

AUSTRALIAN RESEARCH COUNCIL
**Centre of Excellence for
Australian Biodiversity
and Heritage**

OCTOPUS Web Feature Service (WFS) User Guide

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Introduction

OCTOPUS is an open access database of age determinations, organised into five data collections. These data can be viewed and exported through the web interface or accessed directly via Web Feature Service.

This user guide outlines how to use the Web Feature Service (WFS) through third-party software, specifically QGIS and/or R software environment as these software solutions are free and open-source (<https://qgis.org>, <https://www.r-project.org/>).

For an overview of the OCTOPUS database, see:

<https://epicaustralia.org.au/resource/octopus>

<https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100013702>

For detailed information about the OCTOPUS database structure, data collections, and documentation, see: <https://zenodo.org/communities/octopus-database/>

WFS instructions for QGIS

1. After opening QGIS, start a new project: Project > New
2. In the Browser pane, select WFS/OGC API Features > New Connection...

3. Name the new connection (e.g., 'OCTOPUS') and insert the link <http://geoserver.octopusdata.org/geoserver/wfs> in the URL field. Click OK. All available OCTOPUS collections will appear in the Browser pane once a connection is established

4. To add a collection of interest, right click on that collection in the Browser pane and select Add Layer to Project. The collection will appear in the Layers pane. Alternatively, click + drag the layer of interest into the Layers pane
5. To locally store a collection, select Export Layer > To File
6. Select a file format and specify a file name and save location via the '...' button. Select the coordinate reference system (CRS) of choice; OCTOPUS v2 collections use EPSG: 3857 (WGS 84 Pseudo-Mercator)

7. To add a saved shapefile to the project, navigate to the main menu > Layer > Add Layer > Add Vector Layer. Selecting the .shp, .dbf or .shx file (of the six separate files that constitute the shapefile) will open the collection in the Layers pane

Obtaining obfuscated geographical coordinates in QGIS

OCTOPUS data collections SahulArch and FosSahul have obfuscated coordinates from a randomising algorithm set to a 25 km radius range. For these collections, geographical coordinates for datapoints are not stored in the attribute table, or the .csv file if the collection is exported. Follow these steps to obtain obfuscated coordinates (keeping in mind the ≥ 25 km uncertainty) for these collections by calculating polygon centroid points:

1. Navigate to the main menu > Vector > Geometry Tools > Centroids...
2. Select the collection of interest as the Input Layer, and click Run

3. To save coordinates, go to the Processing Toolbox pane and select Vector table > Add X/Y fields to layer
4. Input Layer should appear as the generated centroids, and the coordinate system must be kept as default EPSG: 4326 – WGS84
5. Click Run. This will generate a new layer, Added Fields, in the Layers pane. In the Attribute Table, fields for 'x' (longitude) and 'y' (latitude) will appear at the end of the table with corresponding coordinates for each point feature

WFS instructions for R

OCTOPUS data collections can be accessed using the WFS through R. This section demonstrates how to establish a connection to OCTOPUS and two use cases of accessing and plotting data.

Run the following to load required packages and establish a connection to OCTOPUS. The following requires packages “sf” (simple features support), “httr” (generic web-service package for working with HTTP), “tidyverse” (workhorse collection of R packages for data sciences), “ows4r” (interface for OGC web-services including WFS), “viridis” (colourblind-friendly colour scales for R), and “mapview” (enables map visualisation).

```
# If not installed on your machine yet, run >>  
install.packages(c("sf", "httr", "tidyverse", "ows4r", "viridis",  
"mapview", dependencies = TRUE) << and you'll be all set up
```

```
library(sf)  
library(httr)  
library(tidyverse)  
library(ows4r)  
library(viridis)
```

To store OCTOPUS WFS URL in an object, establish a connection, and show available layers:

```
OCTOPUSdata <- "http://geoserver.octopusdata.org/geoserver/wfs"  
OCTOPUSdata_client <- WFSClient$new(OCTOPUSdata, serviceVersion =  
"2.0.0")  
OCTOPUSdata_client$getFeatureTypes(pretty = TRUE)
```

Running the code above will display the available layers as shown here, with Use case #1 using layer 1 from this list:

	name	title
1	be10-denude:crn_aus_basins	CRN Australian collection: River basins
2	be10-denude:crn_aus_outlets	CRN Australian collection: Sample sites
3	be10-denude:crn_int_basins	CRN Global collection: River basins
4	be10-denude:crn_int_outlets	CRN Global collection: Sample sites
5	be10-denude:crn_xxl_basins	CRN Large basins: River basins
6	be10-denude:crn_xxl_outlets	CRN Large basins: Sample sites
7	be10-denude:crn_inprep_basins	CRN UOW (in preparation): River basins
8	be10-denude:crn_inprep_outlets	CRN UOW (in preparation): Sample sites
9	be10-denude:publications	CRN basin bounding boxes
10	opengeo:countries	Countries of the World
11	be10-denude:expage	ExpAge Database
12	be10-denude:fossahul_webmercator_nrand_25000	FosSahul Database
13	be10-denude:sahularch_osl	Sahul Archaeology: OSL collection
14	be10-denude:sahularch_c14	Sahul Archaeology: Radiocarbon collection
15	be10-denude:sahularch_tl	Sahul Archaeology: TL collection
16	be10-denude:sahulsed_aeolian_osl	Sahul Sedimentary Archives: Aeolian OSL
17	be10-denude:sahulsed_aeolian_tl	Sahul Sedimentary Archives: Aeolian TL
18	be10-denude:sahulsed_fluvial_osl	Sahul Sedimentary Archives: Fluvial OSL
19	be10-denude:sahulsed_fluvial_tl	Sahul Sedimentary Archives: Fluvial TL
20	be10-denude:sahulsed_lacustrine_osl	Sahul Sedimentary Archives: Lacustrine OSL
21	be10-denude:sahulsed_lacustrine_tl	Sahul Sedimentary Archives: Lacustrine TL

> |

Use case #1

In this example, we will plot Australian catchment-averaged ^{10}Be denudation rates. The following will parse the URL into a list:

```
url <- parse_url(OCTOPUSdata)
url$query <- list(service = "wfs",
                 version = "2.0.0",
                 request = "GetFeature",
                 typename = "be10-denude:crn_au_basins",
                 srsName = "EPSG:900913")
```

This is followed by building a request URL from the 'url' list and reading simple features from OCTOPUSdata using the 'request' URL. This may take a few seconds to process:

```
request <- build_url(url)
CRN_AUS_basins <- read_sf(request)
```

Plot the recalculated denudation rate ("EBE_MMKYR") over average slope ("SLP_AVE") from the source "CRN_AUS_basins". This includes setting error bars, scaling points to "AREA" and colour points to average catchment elevation ("ELEV_AVE") using the 'viridis' colour scale, defining axis labels and plot title:

```
myPlot <- ggplot(CRN_AUS_basins, aes(x=SLP_AVE, y=EBE_MMKYR)) +
  geom_errorbar(aes(ymin=(EBE_MMKYR-EBE_ERR),
                  ymax=(EBE_MMKYR+EBE_ERR)), size=0.3, colour="gray80") +
  geom_point(aes(size=AREA, color=ELEV_AVE), alpha=.5) +
  scale_color_viridis(option="C", direction = -1) +
  scale_size_continuous(range = c(2, 10)) +
  xlab("Slope gradient [m km-1]) + ylab("Denudation rate [mm kyr-1]) +
  ggtitle("Australian CRN-derived catchment-wide denudation rates")
+
  theme(plot.title = element_text(size = 20, face = "bold")) +
  labs(size = "Catchment \narea [km2]", colour = "Average
\ncatchment \nelevation [m]")
```

myPlot

This will produce the following plot:

Use case #2

In this example, we will generate an interactive map of fluvial OSL data from SahulSED. The following will load the required “mapview” package and parse the URL into a list:

```
library(mapview)
mapviewOptions(fgb = FALSE)
url2 <- parse_url(OCTOPUSdata)
url2$query <- list(service = "wfs",
                  version = "2.0.0",
                  request = "GetFeature",
                  typename = "be10-denude:sahulshed_fluvial_osl",
                  srsName = "EPSG:900913")
```

This is followed by building a request URL from the ‘url’ list and reading simple features from OCTOPUSdata using the ‘request’ URL. This may take a few seconds to process:

```
request2 <- build_url(url2)
SahulSed.FLV.OSL <- read_sf(request2)
```

Set the coordinate reference system and transform geometry to geographic coordinates, WGS84:

```
SahulSed.FLV.OSL <- st_set_crs(SahulSed.FLV.OSL, 900913)
SahulSed.FLV.OSL = st_transform(SahulSed.FLV.OSL,
                               crs = "+proj=longlat +datum=WGS84")
```

Display on map using the “mapview” package:

```
mapview(SahulSed.FLV.OSL, xcol = "X_WGS84", ycol = "Y_WGS84",
        zcol = "OSL_AGE", at = seq(0, 350, 50), alpha = .25,
        alpha.regions = 0.1, legend = TRUE)
```

This will produce the plot below. Note that the base map can be changed using the “map layers” button, the map will display point ages when hovering over points, and the full record for a point will display when clicked as shown here:

